

PEDAGOGIK FAOLIYAT JARAYONIDA TEXNIKA VA MAHORATNING O'RNI

Mamayakubova Shahlo Ablakulovna

(SamSIFL o'qituvchisi)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7906936>

Annotatsiya: Bugungi kunda mamlakatimiz miqyosida chet tilining roli toboro oshib bormoqda xorijiy tilni o'qitishning ta'limiy maqsadi deb xorijiy tilni o'qitish jarayonida o'quvchilarning dunyokarashini, tafakkurini fikrlash qobiliyatini o'stirish, shu tilni o'zlashtirish orqali o'z ona tilida egallagan bilimlarini takomillashtirish nazarda tutiladi. Bunday holatda ona tili, rus va chet tili tillari o'rtasidagi o'xshashlik va farqlarni bilib olish til o'rganuvchilarning bilim saviyalarini yanada oshiradi. Agar o'zbek tili, rus tili darslarida o'rganilgan bilim, ko'nikma va malakalar ingliz tilini chuqurroq o'rganishga sharoit yaratsa, boshqa fanlar: adabiyot, tarix, geografiya fanlaridan o'rganilgan bilimlar o'quvchilarga jaxon adabiyoti, tarixi va geografiasiga oid bilimlarni ham osonroq egallashga, dunyokarash, mulohazalarining kengayishiga ko'maklashadi.

Tayanch so'zlar: bandlik, qobiliyat, mahorat, ta'lim, tarbiya, malaka, pedagog, xulq-atvori, xarakteri, bilish

Аннотация: Сегодня в нашей стране возрастает роль иностранного языка. Воспитательной целью обучения иностранному языку является развитие у учащихся мировоззрения, мыслительных способностей, совершенствование их знаний на родном языке путем овладения этим языком. В этом случае знание сходств и различий между родным, русским и иностранным языками еще больше повысит уровень знаний изучающих язык. Если знания, навыки и умения, полученные на занятиях по узбекскому и русскому языку, создают условия для более глубокого изучения английского языка, то знания, полученные по другим предметам: литературе, истории, географии, помогут учащимся приобрести знания по мировой литературе, истории, географии. легче, и расширить свое мировоззрение и мнения.

Ключевые слова: занятость, способность, мастерство, образование, обучение, компетентность, педагог, поведение, характер, знания.

Abstract: Today, the role of a foreign language is increasing in our country. The educational goal of foreign language teaching is to develop the worldview, thinking ability of students in the process of teaching a foreign language, and to improve the knowledge acquired in their native language by mastering this language. In this case, knowing the similarities and differences between the

mother tongue, Russian and foreign languages will further increase the knowledge levels of language learners. If the knowledge, skills and abilities learned in Uzbek and Russian language classes create conditions for a deeper study of the English language, the knowledge learned from other subjects: literature, history, and geography will help students to more easily acquire knowledge of world literature, history, and geography, and expand their worldview and opinions.

Key words: employment, ability, skill, education, upbringing, competence, pedagogue, behavior, character, knowledge

Introduction

Although the Republic of Uzbekistan has not yet achieved independence, it has created conditions conducive to the simultaneous development of all industries. Importantly, the development of a continuous educational environment first of all enables a growing number of young people to be employed, and secondly, educated academically and culturally and spiritually to become fully-fledged human beings. Direct instruction is always offered, and each unit is organized with lessons in an age-appropriate sequence for students. Basic subjects such as math, language, and reading are taught in elementary school. Considering that students are sharp-witted at this stage, teaching English to primary school students started from the beginning of the 2013 academic year.

Continuing education. It is the basis of a qualified competitive professional education program, which includes all types of training, national education standards, the structure and institution of the professional education system. [Advanced education. A set of command documents. "East". Tashkent, 2001.google.uz].

The teaching experiences, abilities and skills of today's top teachers in the field of education are the subject of the "Art of Teaching" course.

Methods and materials

The course of study "The art of teaching" has great scientific and practical value in the study of the content, the essence, the structure of this competence, knowledge as a system, in the practice of professional education in higher education. The course "The Art of Teaching" aims to prepare teachers, including future teachers, for educational activities in a scientific, methodical and practical manner. Its primary functions are to develop instructional creativity, ingenuity, instructional communication, teacher presentation, strategies for positively influencing the student from all angles, teaching methods, and teacher education skills.

Teaching methods are based on the teacher's own mental and physical characteristics. Individual teaching methods depend on the teacher's gender, age, client, temperament, physical structure and psychological characteristics [4].

The degree to which teaching skills are practiced reflects the overall preparation of the teacher, that is, the teaching abilities of the individual. If the teacher's speech is inappropriate, negative, negative, unpleasant, and insulting, even the most appropriate words of the teacher may not have an impact on the students, but it can provide the opposite that should come out of it.

Research results

In practical courses, issues such as the culture of teacher talking and thinking, different modes of teaching influence, and teacher teacher organizational competence are studied.

1. Mindfulness and mindfulness exercises are done in practical lessons. Teaching environments are created during hours designated for laboratory and independent work, and are realized through student collaboration. Such challenges or teaching situations serve to develop the teacher's ability to interact with students. The practical courses of the "Teaching Arts" course can be carried out as part of schools and colleges, and are aimed at strengthening theoretical knowledge. The main difference between the course "The art of teaching" and other courses in the teaching program is that it is part of a never-ending creative activity to use the many creative possibilities in the relationship between teacher and student.

2. The concept of teaching skills. After independence, our country, in a very short period of time, has the task of grooming senior professionals who think innovatively and consciously advocate for the development of the country. As a result, the laws "On Education", "National Personnel Training Program" were adopted. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov's speech said, "Perfect ancestors are the foundation of Uzbekistan's future" that deep knowledge alone is not enough to form senior experts and new thinkers. - We don't need graduates, but graduates. With this, the President showed that it is not enough to acquire a solid knowledge, it is necessary to master it and learn knowledge that serves to master the secrets and skills of various professions. The question arises: What is the art of teaching? The art of teaching is insight and knowledge, a practical, authoritative scientific leader who can overcome academic difficulties, the ability to feel the soul and inner world of students, a

prudent and careful approach to the child's the simple and weak personality. and creative courage, scientific inquiry - skills rich in logic and fantasy [3].

3. Teaching skills framework. Teaching skills include the following components.

Human dynamics in the teacher's profession;

Teaching ability, ability

Teaching methods (art) .

Individual tracking in teaching.

1. The lack of teaching skills pedagogy and methodological development leads to the fact that individual teachers undertake creative pursuits independently: how to maintain close relationships with children and teachers? How to get a true snapshot of the relationship between children? seeks answers to the questions.

2. Everyone has talent in one field or another. According to some leading psychologists, the following 6 skills are essential for the teaching profession;

All this can be part of the art of teaching as long as there is an educational goal and it is approached from a humanitarian perspective[2].

. . . . unexpected teaching situations.allows the ability to think and analyze to be maintained. All the mastery of the teacher in the field of teaching methods is evident in the simultaneous demonstration of the practical effect of teaching. Gestures, facial expressions, and movements accompany speech.

4. Among the aspects of teaching skills, the teacher's personal preferences and attitude occupy an important place. His personality is explained by the fact that he has a normal thought process, which enables him to react almost spontaneously to what he sees in many cases. For example, to have another relationship with students, to have a high standard of the student's identity, to believe that none of his students can be mean, and not to tolerate disloyalty.

But such misconceptions can play a negative role. For example, when a colleague is in an out-of-control relationship with a student, instead of confronting her, she defends him. Such deviations can only be prevented if the teacher's interests are sincere and humane.

Conclusions and recommendations

Teaching activity and skills. Pedagogical work is the work of those involved in the education and training of children in the care of people, government and society in order to prepare young people for life, work, and protection of the Motherland. specially prepared for this purpose.

The aim of school teachers' activity is to form a mature, free-thinking man who will build, live and work in a great government-organization in our State. The duty of a teacher to educate a perfect generation and to inculcate in it new

human qualities is the noblest, the highest, and at the same time the noblest and most difficult task. Every student has their own behavior and attitude. It is very difficult to consider and emulate these special qualities in their education and training. For this purpose, they use specific methods that reflect the complexity of interpersonal social relations. Young people who are preparing for the teaching profession need to know its characteristics.

These characteristics of the teaching profession are reflected in the nature of his work. 1) personal characteristics of the teacher; 2) Requirements for teacher instructional and psychological preparation; 3) the scope and content of specialized training; 4) Content in method preparation for specialization.

Strengthening and developing the spirituality of the people is the most important task of the state and society in Uzbekistan. Spirituality is such a precious fruit, formed in the hearts of our ancient and modern people in the great family of mankind along with the love of independence and freedom.

Адабиётлар:

1. Зуфаров Ш. Таълимда инновацион жараёнларни тизимли бошқруви. Назария, таҳлил, тасниф. Т.: 2010.
2. Иномова М. Халқ педагогикаси – оилада болаларнинг маънавий-ахлоқий фазилатларини шакллантиришнинг муҳим воситаси. Халқ таълими журнали, 1995 йил, 4-сон. 33-38 бетлар.
3. Ишмуҳаммедов Р. Инновацион технологиялар ёрдамида таълим самарадорлигини ошириш йўллари. (2-китоб). –Т.: «ТДПУ», 2009. 108 б.
4. Саидахмедов Н. Янги педагогик технологиялар. –Т.: «Молия», 2003. 16-бет.
5. Толипов У., Усмонбоева М. Педагогик технологияларнинг тадбиқий асослари. – Т.:, 2006. 18-бет.

